

POSSIBILITIES OF USING PROBLEM TEACHING METHODS IN ASSESSING THE CONTENT OF SCHOOL STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE IMPROVEMENT

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Abstract: Currently, we know that the process of teaching students in our country takes place in a written, oral and practical way. Because of this, all sorts of incorrect methodological problems arise in the minds of students. This article is also aimed at solving this problem.

Keywords: Practical activities, Discussion and assessment, Individual completion, Individual completion, Scientific research, Projects and projects, Physical cultural activities, Social experiences.

The main part: Problem-based learning means studying the educational material in a way that creates cognitive tasks and problems similar to scientific research in the minds of students. Problematic situations arise in the student's (student's) thinking activity, and they encourage the student (student) to objectively search and learn to draw logically correct scientific conclusions.

Practical activities help students to consolidate theoretical knowledge in practice, to learn concepts and create opportunities for them to apply them in practice. These activities allow students to improve, assimilate and analyze their experiences. The following examples are examples of practical exercises:

- ✚ Scientific research: Allows students to strengthen their theoretical knowledge in practice by conducting scientific research, collecting and analyzing data.
- ✚ Projects and Projects: Helps students to develop their mastery by giving them the opportunity to create projects on a topic and develop them in practice.
- ✚ Physical and cultural activities: Sports, music, painting, theater and other physical activities help students to develop the mastery content.
- ✚ Social experiences: Gives students the opportunity to develop content through active participation in the community, discussion of social issues and community service.

These practical exercises will help the development of students' learning content and their development.

Schools have several methods for assessing student learning content, including:

- Tests and exams: Conducting tests and exams to test the knowledge level of the students. This method helps to determine how much knowledge students have.
- Portfolios: Assessment of mastery content by creating portfolios in which students collect their own work (projects, articles, graphics, etc.).
- Discussion and evaluation: Assessing the content of the mastery by discussing with teachers or other students the coursework, projects and other work that the student has prepared.
- Individual Completion: Communicating with each student individually, identifying their goals, challenges, and assessing their mastery.

Problem-based education is a subjective form of expressing the need to develop scientific knowledge. It is a situation that objectively arises between knowledge and ignorance in the process of the development of a new society. A problem situation is a certain mental state of the student, which arises due to the realization of a conflict in the process of completing a certain task.

Conclusion: The complexity of the problem chosen for the problem situation method should correspond to the knowledge levels of the learners. They must be able to find a solution to the given problem, otherwise, failure to find a solution will lead to the loss of interest and self-confidence of learners.

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